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Security and environmental assessment of the upscaled 10 000 tpa recycling process

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1 Introduction and summary

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document presents environmental and security assessment of the upscaled recycling line (10kt/y) based on pyrolysis, mechanical sorting and mild chemical etching.

1.2 Structure

This document is structured as follows:

Section 1 is an introduction chapter

Section 2 describes the impact study

1.3 Relationship with other documents

The present document will be completed with:

D4.1 An equipment design of the continuous pyrolysis process (M11)

D4.2 A constructed and operational equipment realizing continuous pyrolysis process (M27)

D4.3 An integrated quality control system along the recycling process (M45)

D4.5 Demonstration campaign of the industrial recycling line (M47)

2 Impact study

2.1 Description of the initial state of the environment and factors likely to be significantly affected by the project

2.1.1 *Environmental issues near the project*

The project is located in the commune of Saint Honoré, in the department of Isère (FRANCE).

The following table presents the main environmental issues surrounding the location of the planned facilities:

TABLE 1: MAIN ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES NEAR THE PROJECT

Environmental compartment		Main elements of the initial state of the environment According to	Stakes
Town planning and easements	Local Urban Plan (ENJOYED)	the PLU regulations, approved on March 20, 2014, then amended on February 26, 2015, the area on which the project site is located is classified as "urban area of economic activity". As such, industrial and craft activities are authorized there under special conditions, in terms of access and roads, service by networks, conditions of location, height and exterior appearance, parking and green spaces.	No
	Consistency Schema Territorial	Neither the study perimeter nor the municipality of Saint-Honoré are concerned by a Territorial Coherence Scheme.	No
	Utility easements public (UP)	Following the site restoration work carried out by the Matheysine Community of Communes after the purchase of the facilities from the former operator, a public utility easement (SUP) was established in connection with the residual pollution in order to keep a record of the contamination present and guarantee uses compatible with the quality of the site's soils. Two public utility easements have also been identified nearby: - About 300 m to the southeast and 500 m to the west of the site: area covered by an SUP linked to a Risk Prevention Plan Predictable Natural Resources (PPRNP) and Mining Risk Prevention Plan (PPRM) (PM1) - About 300 m to the east and 600 m to the west of the site: area covered by an SUP relating to the establishment of pipelines electrical.	Weak
Human environment and activities around site	Population	The town of Saint-Honoré has 818 inhabitants in 2018 according to the INSEE census, for a density of 56.1 inhabitants per km ² .	No
	Economic context	In 2018, the municipality had 510 workers, i.e. 72.2% of the population of working age (from 15 to 64 years old); 64.3% of workers were employed. Between 2008 and 2018, the number of unemployed doubled in the municipality. The economic development of the commune is undergoing a discreet and irregular evolution with around sixty companies set up over the last decade, 78% of which are sole proprietorships. Industry represents 42.9% of the municipality's economic activity, excluding agriculture.	No
	Tourism and leisure	Tourist activity is almost nil within the scope of the study. According to INSEE data for 2020, no hotel, campsite, collective accommodation or sports center is listed in the town of Saint-Honoré. Regarding the leisure offer focused on outdoor activities (walks, hikes, etc.), the town has a Departmental Plan for Walking and Hiking Routes (PDIPR). To the south-west of the planned site and outside the study perimeter, departing from La Mure, the Petit Train de la Mure is the area's main tourist interest.	No
	Residential/tertiary/ERP activities	The closest dwellings are close to the site: about 30 m from the buildings. Public facilities and establishments open to the public have been inventoried within a perimeter of 2 km around the site. They are located and identified. No hospital, retirement home, kindergarten, university or regular line station has been identified within the scope of the study.	AVERAGE

Environmental compartment	Main elements of the initial state of the environment	Stakes
	<p>Networks of communications</p> <p><u>Main highways :</u> The plot concerned by the project is bordered by the departmental roads D114D to the south (called "Route de la mouche") and D115C to the east (called "Route du Tabor"). About 950 m to the west, the RN85 national road (known as the "Route de Napoléon") connects the town of Vizille with the town of Gap, passing through the town of La Mure just 3 km south of the plot.</p> <p><u>Railways :</u> The rail network around the site is only represented by the Petit Train de La Mure railway line, which is touristic in nature. Closest to the site, the railway line is approximately 1.5 km west of the proposed site.</p> <p><u>Public transport:</u> The business area is served by Transisère line 4100, linking La Mure and Grenoble. The stop (ZI Le Marais La Mure) is located 1 km west of the site, on the RN 85. In addition, the small local PSHNA line and a school line connect the Espace Evolutif business area and its surroundings with the village of Saint-Honoré. The stop is located on the D115C, at the level of the northeast corner of the plot.</p> <p><u>Airports and airfields</u> No airport or aerodrome is identified in or near the study area.</p>	No
	<p>Networks</p> <p><u>Waters:</u> A pipe taking care of the rainwater from all the buildings of the Espace Evolutif will drain 150 m to the south, on the other side of the D114D road, at the level of ru La Mouche. The eastern part of the Evolutive Space on which CEG will be established will be equipped with a device allowing the containment of fire extinguishing water.</p> <p><u>Gas :</u> The Espace Evolutif site is not connected to the town gas network. However, there are buried propane tanks allowing the gas supply of the companies established within the Evolutive Space.</p> <p><u>Electricity :</u> Power lines run along the activity zone from north to south about 300 m to the east and 600 m to the west. At the site level, a low voltage network (400 V) supplies all sectors of the business area. As part of the rehabilitation and modularization project of the "Evolutive Space", new tracings are redesigned for the drinking water supply network and the electricity network. Telecom networks, rainwater and gas, non-existent, are also created.</p>	AVERAGE

Environmental compartment	Main elements of the initial state of the environment Waste		Stakes
	Waste	<p>management on the territory of the commune of Saint-Honoré is carried out by the Community of communes of Matheysine. Saint-Honoré has a single waste collection center in the town (in Fugières, north of the site), accessible to the inhabitants of the town. The inter-municipal recycling center of La Mure, as well as the recycling centers of Sousville, Laval dens, Corps, Valbonnais and Salle-en-Beaumont are also available to Saint-Honoré.</p> <p><u>Regional plan for development, sustainable development and territorial equality (SRADDET) Auvergne Rhône-Alpes:</u></p> <p>The SRADDET Auvergne Rhône-Alpes, approved by order of the regional prefect on 04/10/2020, sets objectives for 2030 with regard to waste management, among other things, as well as air quality, energy management, innovation and the development of the circular economy.</p>	Weak
Historical, cultural and landscape heritage	Listed buildings or registered	No listed or listed building has been identified in or near the study area.	No
	ZPPA	<p>No area of presumed archaeological prescriptions (ZPPA) has been identified within the scope of the study.</p> <p>Nearby, the ZAPP no. 221995 "Zone unique Le Bourg" is listed in the municipality of La Mure (decree of 01/04/2004), 2.6 km south-west of the plot where the project is located.</p>	No
	Classified or registered sites	<p>No classified or registered site has been identified within a radius of 2 km around the site that is the subject of this study.</p> <p>Nearby, a listed site has been identified 3 km northwest of the plot, corresponding to a portion of the RN85 "Route de Napoléon" (203S3, 304S3, 462S3) as it passes through the municipalities of Laffrey, Pierre-Chatel and Saint-Theoffrey.</p> <p>Also outside the study perimeter, the classified site of the "Rock of the Pierced Stone" (decree of April 4, 1911) is located 4.4 km northwest of the planned site.</p>	No
	Remarkable heritage sites and historical monuments	<p>No remarkable heritage site has been identified in the study area.</p> <p>Nearby, a protected area under the surroundings of historical monuments (AC1) n° 1906273359 "Saint Baptiste Church" has been identified in the town of Mayres-Savel (ministerial decree of 20/09/1919), 8 km southwest of the project.</p>	No
	Countryside	<p>Territory with a strong agricultural identity, with a predominance of crops all along the plateau of La Matheysine dotted with small discontinuous urban fabrics, with the exception of the urban and peri-urban perimeter of La Mure, which has a significant surface area.</p> <p>To the east and west of the site, deciduous and coniferous forests associated with the relief of the neighboring massifs delimit the landscape of the study perimeter, which is essentially agricultural and grassland.</p> <p>Indeed, adjacent to the RN85, the activity zone represents a kind of industrial island surrounded by a mosaic of crops and fields, dotted with small clusters of scattered dwellings. As for the site, it is bordered to the north by the Pré des Sagnes, and to the east by houses and then by cultivated plots punctuated by small wooded areas. To the south and west, other existing buildings house industrial and craft activities.</p>	No
Traffic	The average annual daily traffic on the D115C was 700 vehicles per day in 2018. The average annual daily traffic on the RN 85 was 6,000 vehicles per day.		Weak

Environmental compartment	Main elements of the initial state of the environment Natural		Stakes
Natural environment	Natural areas remarkable	<p><u>Areas of Ecological, Faunistic and Floristic Interest (ZNIEFF) type I and II:</u></p> <p>As part of the study perimeter, a ZNIEFF type I zone has been identified about 200 m to the northwest and about 300 m to the south: ZNIEFF type I (820031990): "Bas Marais du Villaret", on a area of 87 ha.</p> <p>Other type I ZNIEFFs have been identified within a radius of 2 km around the site:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nantes-en-Ratier marsh (820031989) over an area of 18 ha 1.3 km east of the site, 2. Humid meadow of the citadel (820031988) over an area of 45 ha 900 m south of the site, 3. Marais des Lauzes (820031992) over an area of 6 ha 1.1 km west of the site, 4. Etang du Crey (820031995) over an area of 32 ha 1.9 km northwest of the site. <p>With regard to the ZNIEFF type II zones, the entire project site is included within the perimeter of a ZNIEFF type II (820009967): "Lakes and wetlands of the Matheysin plateau" (2475 ha).</p> <p><u>Natura 2000 sites:</u></p> <p>The site is not affected by any Natura 2000 zone, the closest sites being the FR8201753 site "Forets, moors and hay meadows on the slopes of the Col d'Ormon" (Habitats Directive), about 7 km to the south-east. , and the site FR9310036 "Les Ecrins" (Birds Directive), about 13 km east of the plot.</p> <p><u>Important Bird Areas (IBA):</u></p> <p>The study area is not affected by any IBAs.</p>	AVERAGE
	Wet area	<p>According to the inventory of wetlands in Rhône-Alpes Auvergne, no wetlands have been identified within the scope of the project's location. However, several wetlands, including a few peat bogs, have been identified all around the Espace Evolutif activity zone, to the north-west, south and east of the site.</p> <p><u>Prefectural Order for the Protection of the Biotope:</u></p> <p>In line with this inventory of wetlands of significant ecological value, a prefectural decision of September 9, 2010 established a biotope protection perimeter for the Marais de La Mure peat bog. This perimeter concerns part of the study area and surrounds the project site, which is not directly concerned.</p> <p>Within its framework, a series of specific prescriptions in terms of maintenance, pollution prevention, layout and circulation apply.</p> <p><u>Sites concerned by the RAMSAR Convention on Wetlands of International Importance:</u></p> <p>According to the mapping of RAMSAR zones in France, no RAMSAR site has been identified at municipal level.</p>	Weak

Environmental compartment	Main elements of the initial state of the environment		Stakes
	Ecological inventories	<p>Flora</p> <p>Species of protected flora are present in the commune of Saint-Honoré, two of which benefit from national protection status, as "strictly protected species". Given the habitats of these 2 species, their presence on the site's green spaces is unlikely.</p> <p>Among the other species inventoried in the municipality, one is also listed on one of the ZNIEFF sheets located nearby. This is a fern generally found in shady places, woods or ravines. Its presence on the site is therefore unlikely.</p>	Weak
		<p>Wildlife</p> <p>The study area is home to a few threatened and/or protected species that are the subject of a National or Regional Action Plan (PNA – PRA). Note the presence of:</p> <p><u>Chiroptera (bats)</u> common pipistrelle Leisler's moth</p> <p><u>Avifauna (birds)</u> Bearded vulture. Although present in the study area, it is not included in its breeding territory. Moreover, if an overflight of the site by the bearded vulture at high altitude is possible, its presence near the planned installations is unlikely and would be fortuitous.</p> <p><u>Amphibians (batrachians)</u> Yellow Belly Ringer. The project site is located within its range (data from 1996 to 2016). However, the semi-natural habitats present on the site do not constitute terrestrial habitats favorable to amphibians, as there are no water points on the site. Its presence on the site is therefore unlikely and would be fortuitous.</p> <p>The commune of Saint-Honoré does not present any major challenges with regard to terrestrial mammals (large fauna, small carnivores and micro-mammals).</p>	Weak
	Regional Scheme of Ecological Coherence (SRCE)	The SRCEs of the former Auvergne and Rhône-Alpes Regions were repealed by order of the Regional Prefect of April 10, 2020. Since that date, it is the SRADDET Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes which replaces the SRCEs and which constitutes the framework document at the regional scale for the definition and implementation of the green and blue infrastructure.	Weak

Environmental compartment		Main elements of the initial state of the environment The site is	Stakes
Ground and basement	General geology	<p>located on the plateau of La Matheysine, bordered to the east by the foothills of Tabor and Piquet de Nantes, and to the west by the flanks of Conest and Senepy. Structurally, the plateau of La Matheysine corresponds to a horst of secondary land, of Jurassic to Cretaceous age, generally north-south in orientation. Erosion reveals at the heart of this structure a metamorphic base surmounted by important carboniferous series. Quaternary deposits (moraines, alluvium and colluvium) cover the bottoms of topographic depressions.</p> <p>On a local scale, the site is located in a relatively flat and marshy area, corresponding to the Marais de La Mure. This one was formed following the filling of a lake which extended to the maximum of the Würm between the glacial tongues of the Bonne and the Romanche.</p> <p>According to the Bureau of Geological and Mining Research (BRGM), the project site is located on an Fz2 Post-Würm or Holocene layer: fluvial alluvium of major beds.</p> <p>The fluvial formations essentially boil down to the old terrace (early Würm) of the "basal alluvium" of the Drac, thick (up to 100 m) gravel with coarse pebbles, filling an interglacial valley of similar depth to the current one, fossilized by the Wurmian glaciolacustrine formations and largely outcropping on the slopes of the Drac and the Bonne.</p>	No
	Topography	<p>This territory, whose average altitude is greater than 1,000 meters, includes several natural regions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • in the western part, Matheysine, Trièves and Beaumont, • in the central and eastern part, the south of the Taillefer massif (Tabor, Piquet de Nantes, Armet and Coiro) and the western edge of the Ecrins – Pelvoux massif (Rochail, Signal de Lauvitel, Pic de Valsenestre, Roche de la Muzelle, Tête du Clotonnet). <p>The Matheysine extends between the lakes of Laffrey (lakes of Petichet and Pierre-Châtel) to the confluence of the Drac and the Bonne. It is a plateau bordered to the east by the foothills of Tabor and Piquet de Nantes and to the west by the flanks of Conest and Sénéppy (Genépi on the maps) which culminate on the neighboring leaf, La Chapelle-en-Vercors.</p>	No

Environmental compartment		Main elements of the initial state of the environment 2 sites	Stakes
	soil pollution	<p>(ALLIBERT and TECUMSEH) are listed in the BASIAS database (of former industrial sites and service activities) within the scope of the project or in its immediate environment.</p> <p>Only 1 site is listed in the BASOL database (which lists polluted sites and soils) over a perimeter of 2 km around the site, corresponding to the plastics processing activity previously carried out on the Espace Evolutif site on which implement the CEG project.</p> <p>Depollution operations were carried out in July 2013 at the level of the old fuel oil tank and between November 2015 and February 2016 at the level of the old production hall. They consisted of excavating and sending the polluted materials off-site, combined with treatment of groundwater at the bottom of the excavation and cleaning of the service galleries.</p> <p>At the end of this work, residual contamination remains present at the right of the site.</p> <p>The studies carried out (in particular an analysis of residual risks) conclude that the site is compatible with a future use of an industrial or artisanal type, subject to certain rules requiring the establishment of public utility easements (aiming to keep in memory the presence of residual contamination, as well as construction constraints and resulting usage restrictions).</p>	AVERAGE
Surface waters	Hydrographic network	<p>The study area is part of the Drac watershed. The Drac, a tributary of the Isère, has its source in the heart of the Écrins massif, in the Hautes-Alpes department. This watercourse is made up of 4 lakes (Lac Mort, Grand Lac de Laffrey, Lac de Petichet and Lac de Pierre-Châtel) and in turn receives numerous tributaries in the department of Isère: the Sèzia, the Bonne, the Ebron, the Jonche, the Vaulx stream, the Gresse, the Lavanchon and the Romanche.</p> <p>Located on the right-of-way of an old filled-in lake, the plateau also includes marshes and peat bogs.</p> <p>The site is located on the right bank of the La Mouche stream. This flows west and joins La Jonche about 1 km south-west of the site. La Mouche is the outlet for many rainwater networks in the Marais industrial zone, including the rainwater network for the Espace Evolutif site.</p>	AVERAGE
	State of waterways	<p>No hydrological station is listed by the Rhône-Mediterranean water agency on the La Mouche stream. On the other hand, there is a station on the Jonche, at a place called La Roche, downstream from La Mure (station no. 06142687). The data from 2013 to 2020 show generally good physico-chemical readings, but highlight an average to poor ecological state with the presence of nitrites. As the chemical status is historically characterized by the presence of benzo(a)pyrene-type substances, it has generally improved since 2017.</p>	Strong
	SDAGE Rhone Mediterranean	<p>The Rhône Méditerranée Water Development and Management Master Plan (2016 – 2021) was approved at the end of 2015.</p>	AVERAGE

Environmental compartment		Main elements of the initial state of the environment The scope of	Stakes
	SAGE of the Drac and the Romansh	<p>the Drac and Romanche Water Development and Management Plan, voted by the CLE on December 10, 2018, covers an area of 2,575 km² and covers 117 municipalities. It extends over 2 regions (Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes and Provence-Alpes-Côte D'azur) and 3 departments: Isère (113 municipalities), Savoie (2 municipalities) and Hautes-Alpes (2 municipalities) . The waterways of the territory are structured around the main valleys of the Drac and the Romanche:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the Drac and its 6 main tributaries: the Sézia, the Bonne, the Jonche, the Ebron, the Gresse and the Lavanchon; - the Romanche and its 7 main tributaries: the Ferrand, the Vénéon, the Sarenne, the Rive, the Lignarre, the Eau d'Olle and the Vernon. <p>A "Drac Isérois Rivers Contract" was signed in May 2018, making it possible to ensure the maintenance of the consultation, the dynamics present on the territory of the Drac Isérois and the progress of the actions implemented.</p>	AVERAGE
Underground waters	Hydrogeology	<p>The planned site is located at the right of the deep groundwater body "Domaine plissé BV Romanche et Drac" (water body code: FRDG407) which is the subject of a catchment in the municipality of Nantes-en-Ratier (about 24 km from the site).</p> <p>Springs from fissured and karstic aquifers emerge at the foot of the slopes, in contact with the stony silt alluvium of the valleys. Flow variations are significant, mainly related to snowmelt. The water reserves are renewed by the impluvium.</p> <p>The fluvial and torrential deposits encountered to the right of the Espace Evolutif site are the seat of a shallow aquifer (about 1 to 2 meters deep) with a direction of flow oriented towards the southwest, towards the stream of La Mouche.</p> <p>Given the shallow depth of groundwater and the hydrographic network, the possibility of aquifer/river exchange cannot be ruled out.</p>	AVERAGE
	Water supply drinkable	<p>Data from the Rhône-Mediterranean Water Agency, based on the 2009 and 2013 fee, lists 12 water catchments within a radius of 5 km around the site, including 10 intended for drinking water supply and 2 intended for economic uses.</p> <p>Considering the topography of the sector, the supposed direction of flow of groundwater (oriented towards the southwest) and the possible supply of the water table by the superficial hydrographic network (itself supplied by the sources present in the sector) none catchment is not present downstream of the site.</p> <p>Furthermore, the site is not included in any DWS catchment protection perimeter.</p>	No
	Area of distribution of waters	<p>The project site is not located in a water distribution zone.</p>	No

Environmental compartment		Main elements of the initial state of the environment An air quality	Stakes
Air quality	Air quality in the area	<p>report was carried out by Atmo Auvergne-Rhône Alpes for the year 2019 in the department of Isère (38).</p> <p>Despite the steady improvement in air quality, pollution episodes persist, with temporary but marked increases in pollutant concentrations.</p> <p>Regarding the distribution of activations between pollutants, Ozone was responsible for two thirds of atmospheric vigilance, the trend towards the predominance of this pollutant has been confirmed since 2018. This seems to be due both to less harsh winters and to anticyclones more marked with higher temperatures in summer.</p> <p>On the territory, the closest measuring station to the site is that of Vif in the south of Grenoble, located about 17 km north-west of the site at an altitude of 310 m, in a peri-urban/industrial environment. These measurements cannot accurately reflect the air quality at the site level, located in rural areas. However, the stations identified in similar conditions - Lans-en-Vercors or Les Ecrins - do not measure all the pollutants targeted by this initial state. Consequently, in the absence of other options, the measurements of the Vif station will provide an upper frame of reference in the study of the current state of the environment.</p>	AVERAGE
	Regional Air Climate and Energy Plan	The Regional Air Climate and Energy Plan (SRCAE) for the Rhône-Alpes region was approved in June 2012, for the period from 2014 to 2019. This document aims to encompass the approaches to controlling the energy demand, the fight against atmospheric pollution, the development of renewable energies and the fight against climate change and its effects.	AVERAGE
	Regional Wind Power Scheme	The regional wind power scheme (SRE) , which is part of the SRCAE, was canceled by judgment of the administrative court of Lyon for the Auvergne region as well as for the Rhône-Alpes region for lack of environmental assessment.	No
	Protection Plan the atmosphere	The study area is not affected by any Atmosphere Protection Plan.	No
	Climate-Air-Energy Plan Territorial	As of September 1, 2021, no Territorial Climate-Air-Energy Plan has been initiated by the Community of Municipalities of Matheysine.	No

Environmental compartment		Main elements of the initial state of the environment The sound	Stakes
Sound environment	Initial sound state	environment is mainly impacted by the boilermaking work from the workshops located in the western part of the building. Added to this is the road traffic noise generated by the various vehicles passing over the site, as well as on the roads located nearby. Environmental sound levels are generally between 49 and 59 dB(A) during the day and between 38 and 44 dB(A) during the night.	AVERAGE
	Noise prevention plan	The study area is not affected by a Noise Prevention Plan.	No
Olfactory environment		The site is located within an existing business area, in a rural environment. Odors are potentially present linked to agricultural, artisanal and industrial activities in the activity area.	Weak
Climate data	Temperature and sunshine	The annual average temperature is 9.6°C over the period from 1981 to 2010, with a measured minimum of -20.7°C (recorded on January 7, 1985) and a maximum of 37°C (recorded on July 7, 2015). and August 19, 2012). No data on sunshine duration is available.	No
	Rainfall	Rainfall is fairly constant throughout the year, with peaks in May and September of 95.6mm and 95.4mm respectively, and a minimum of 58mm in July. The average annual rainfall rate is 934.8 mm. The daily precipitation record dates from December 21, 1991 and stands at 94.1 mm.	No
	Wind regime	The prevailing winds come mainly from the South, South-East and North-West. As an approximation, the average annual wind speed is around 12 km/h.	No

Thus, the environmental issues around the site are on the whole nil, low or average; with the exception of the “State of the watercourses” aspect deemed to be “Strong”.

2.1.2 Likely evolution of the environment in the event of project implementation and in the absence of project implementation

To enable the impact of the project to be assessed in all areas, it is necessary to establish one or more possible scenarios for maintaining the land without the project. The reference scenario aims to compare the project site to what the site could have been without all the modifications induced by it.

In the case of a plot located in an industrial zone (zone classified as "urban zone of economic activity" to the PLU), with an environmental liability (a public utility easement has been established in connection with residual pollution), the land is not conducive to the development of activities other than industrial or artisanal.

The only foreseeable evolution of the initial state of the environment (in the event of realization of the project or not) concerns the landscape.

The facades (currently of disparate aspects) will be standardized by the Community of Communes of Matheysine within the framework of the operations of partial demolition, rehabilitation and change of destination of the rental modular workshops which have been the subject of a building permit. build issued on 09/22/2017 by the municipality of Saint-Honoré. White will be the only color of the facades. The concrete foundations of the platforms will be painted brown dark.

The demolition operations have already been carried out in 2018 by the Community of Communes.

These works are independent of the project, and the company ROSI ALPES will take place in the premises after this renovation.

2.2 Description of possible significant impacts of the project on the environment

2.2.1 Land impacts

No agricultural land will be consumed since the project will be located on a pre-existing industrial site.

The green space zones will not be modified on the right of the ROSI ALPES site.

The impact on land is therefore nil.

2.2.2 Impact on water resources

The ROSI ALPES site will be supplied by the public drinking water supply network at 2 points which will be equipped with meters and backflow preventers:

- The first for **sanitary uses** (consumption estimated at approximately **350 m³ /year** based on a daily consumption of 50 liters/day/employee and at most 330 working days/year),
- The second for industrial **uses** (consumption estimated at **6,356 m³ /year**). Water for industrial use be used for:
 - To compensate for water losses by evaporation in the wet scrubber of the effluents hot air from the pyrolysis furnace,
 - In the treatment baths of the chemical/etching treatment machine,
 - In the rinsing baths of the chemical treatment/etching machine.

This industrial water consumption will not impact the municipal resources. Indeed, the municipality distributes an annual volume of more than 300,000 m³, this by using only part of the available water catchment.

It is likely that the water used in the treatment and rinsing baths of the chemical treatment/etching machine could be recycled in the wet scrubber of atmospheric effluents of the pyrolysis furnace. Thus, depending on the results of the tests that will be carried out after the commissioning of the planned facilities, water consumption could possibly be reduced to approximately 4,830 m³ / year (i.e. a reduction of approximately 1,525 m³ /year in consumption drinking water).

In addition, the site will study the possibilities of implementing cascade rinsing after the 1st chemical etching step, which could make it possible to reduce water consumption in the rinsing baths by 294 m³

2.2.3 Impacts on surface waters

2.2.3.1 Effluent identification

The different categories of effluent from the site will be as follows:

- Sanitary water,
- Rainwater flowing down the roads,
- Roof rainwater (free of pollution).

The site has separate networks for each of these effluents.

There will be no discharge of industrial water because:

- Used baths from the processing/etching workshop will be packaged in 1 m³ containers/IBCs and stored inside the building before being evacuated as waste.
- Scrubber drains during maintenance operations will also be packaged in containers/IBC of 1 m³ and evacuated as waste
- **All treatment facilities and their ancillary facilities (storage of liquid products, storage of used baths, scrubber of pyrolysis and post-combustion gases, dust collectors, etc.) will be located inside the buildings.**
There will therefore be no entrainment of pollution by leaching of the equipment by bad weather.

The impact of the discharge of sanitary water and rainwater from roads is presented in the following paragraphs.

2.2.3.2 Impact of sanitary water discharges

Sanitary water will be discharged into the collective sanitation network of the Jonche Intermunicipal Sanitation Syndicate (SIAJ), which includes the municipalities of La Mure, Saint-Honoré and Susville.

They are then treated by the wastewater treatment plant located in the municipality of La Mure (which has a capacity of 11,350 equivalent inhabitants) which treats the wastewater of the municipalities of the SIAJ, as well as that of the municipalities of Ponsonnas and Prunières. The treated water is then discharged into the Champagne stream, a tributary of the Bonne.

Given the fact that the discharges are limited to discharges of sanitary water previously treated by a treatment plant, **the impact linked to the discharges of sanitary water is considered to be low.**

2.2.3.3 Qualitative impact of rainwater discharges

The pollution associated with rainwater flowing down the yard's roads can be qualified as follows:

- Suspended matter: earth, etc. from vehicle traffic,
- Chemical oxygen demand (COD): represents the resources likely to consume oxygen in the water, for example organic compounds (such as oils) or mineral salts,
- Hydrocarbons: oils, fuels... resulting from the passage of vehicles.
-

The intensity of this pollution is difficult to assess, it depends in particular on the characteristics of the rain and the period of dry weather preceding the rain.

The terrain of the Espace Evolutif is relatively flat. However, a slight difference in levels (approximately 1 m) is noticeable between the southern part and the northern part. This has made it possible in the past to develop service yards serving platforms on one side and level of access on the other.

Currently, rainwater collected in the courtyard located between sectors 4 and 5 is discharged without treatment into the Mouche river.

During the site development work prior to the installation of ROSI ALPES, the courtyard's rainwater collection network will be completely taken over, and a rainwater treatment device of the hydrocarbon separator type (class 1 and a capacity of 15 L/s) will be put in place. This will be emptied periodically to ensure its treatment efficiency.

A manhole will be set up at the outlet of the separator to allow samples to be taken.

Downstream of this manhole, road water will join a pipe which will also collect rainwater from roofs (not likely to be polluted).

Given the fact that discharges are limited to discharges of rainwater previously treated by a hydrocarbon separator and whose quality will comply with the applicable regulations, **the impact related to liquid discharges is considered to be low.**

2.2.3.4 Quantitative impact of stormwater discharges

The impacts of a project in terms of surface hydrology are linked to increases in flows linked to the sealing of drained watersheds. Rainwater discharges can in fact induce a change in the flow of receiving environments, particularly when these have low hydrological regimes or low flow capacities.

The consequences are then felt on the downstream part of the outfalls and/or rivers where the overflow phenomena can be amplified. An additional and significant contribution of rainwater can generate new overflow phenomena or worsen an existing situation.

Given the fact that the waterproof surface will not be increased compared to the current situation, **the impact of the project from a quantitative point of view will be nil.**

2.2.3.5 Containment of fire extinguishing water

The containment of fire extinguishing water will be carried out by isolating the rainwater connection point of the eastern part of Espace Evolutif. The water will then be confined in the underground network as well as on the surface of the outer courtyard located to the east of sector 4.

2.2.4 Impacts on soil, subsoil and groundwater

2.2.4.1 Public utility easements related to the presence of residual soil contamination.

The project is located opposite a former site operated by various successive companies between 1972 and 2013.

Following the cessation of activities of the last operator in 2013, a soil diagnosis was carried out, which revealed the presence of significant contamination of the soil by total hydrocarbons to the right of an old buried fuel tank and to the right from the studio hall. In line with the latter, the groundwater, present at shallow depths, also showed contamination by hydrocarbons (presence of floating).

Despite depollution operations carried out between 2013 and 2016, residual contamination is present at the right of the site. Public utility easements (SUP) were instituted by prefectural decree n°DDPP-IC-2019-03-63 of March 25, 2019, in order to keep in mind the presence of

residual contamination, as well as construction constraints and restrictions of use which arise so that residual contamination on the site remains compatible with industrial or artisanal use.

The ROSI ALPES project will be located partially in line with the residual contamination. The constraints and restrictions defined by the Easements of Public Utility will be respected within the framework of the project, in particular:

- The maintenance of the recoveries at the level of the contaminated zones,
- The passage of drinking water pipes outside the contaminated areas (buried in the east courtyard of the Evolutionary Space, then overhead in the building),
- Compliance with the minimum sizes of the premises (20 m², 2.44 m under the ceiling, and renewal rate minimum air flow of 0.37 times per hour),
- Lack of use of groundwater.

2.2.4.2 Project impact

The premises in which liquid products likely to create water or soil pollution will be stored or used will be designed with retention or equipped with appropriate retention.

IBC loading/unloading operations will be carried out in a sealed area; during these operations, the site will be placed in retention by isolation of the ROSI ALPES road water connection point to the Espace Evolutif network.

Taking into account all the planned measures, **the operation of the site will therefore have no impact on the soil and groundwater.**

2.2.5 Impacts on biodiversity

2.2.5.1 Issues identified

The inventory of Natural Areas of Ecological, Faunistic and Floristic Interest (ZNIEFF) aims to carry out an inventory of the most interesting areas from an ecological point of view and present a good state of conservation. Its presence is proof of the ecological richness and the quality of the territory's natural environment. But it has no legal effect and **it is not an instrument of regulatory protection**. Two types of ZNIEFF are distinguished:

- Type I ZNIEFF designating “ sectors of a generally limited area characterized by the presence of species, associations of species or rare, remarkable environments, or characteristics of the environment of the regional or national natural heritage”. They identify in particular rare or rare species, at the edge of their distribution area.
- Type II ZNIEFF designating “ *large natural sites that are rich and little modified, or that offer significant biological potential* “. These are generally areas without strictly protected species but singular areas.

The project is included in the perimeter of the ZNIEFF type II n°820009967 “ *Lakes and wetlands of the Matheysin plateau* ” which occupies 2,475 hectares.

It is a wet plateau occupied by numerous lakes and marshy lands. These wetlands contain natural environments of great interest (meadows), as well as many remarkable species of flora, birds, fish, batrachians and chiroptera.

In addition, another type I ZNIEFF zone is present about 200 m to the northwest and about 300 m to the south: this is ZNIEFF n°820031990: "Bas Marais du Villaret" which occupies an area of 87 hectares. These are marshes dominated by herbaceous plants, small brown mosses and many species with colorful flowers.

No wetlands have been identified within the perimeter of the project, but several wetlands (including a few peat bogs) have been identified all around the activity zone, to the northwest, south and east of the site. In particular, the Marais de La Mure peat bog located 300 m to the south-east of the project is protected by a biotope protection order (site FR3800766).

Threatened and/or protected fauna species subject to a National or Regional Action Plan likely to be found on the site consist of chiroptera (bats).

The presence of protected flora on the site is considered unlikely.

2.2.5.2 Impact of the ROSI ALPES site

ROSI ALPES will be set up on a previously developed site. **No natural spaces will be consumed** within the geographical perimeter that ROSI ALPES will operate.

Prior to the start of operations, ROSI ALPES will fit out the buildings and set up the facilities. Given the low stakes of the site, this limited work carried out mainly inside buildings may have a low and reversible impact on biodiversity due to the disturbance of species.

In the operational phase, the site's activities may have a very low impact on biodiversity, linked to truck traffic and low noise emissions.

Regarding bat populations likely to be present, the industrial nature of the buildings is not conducive to hosting breeding colonies or isolated individuals.

A few high-stemmed trees (eight) are present in the green spaces. These will be kept as part of the project.

The site constitutes a limited hunting territory due to its waterproofing (which will not be increased as part of the project). The project will have only a very low impact on bats.

Given the absence of water abstraction (other than that from the drinking water supply network), the project will have no impact on wetlands.

Given the distance (7 kilometers) separating the ROSI ALPES site from the nearest Natura 2000 area, the site will have no impact on Natura 2000 sites.

2.2.6 Impacts on other natural resources

The impacts of the project on land, soil, water and biodiversity have been presented in the previous paragraphs.

For the past 20 years, the photovoltaic market has been driven by the technology of solar panels based on crystalline silicon, which have a lifespan of 20 to 35 years. The wave of development of the photovoltaic market in Europe, which began in the 2000s, is currently resulting in the beginning of a wave of end-of-life panels that must be recycled. In addition, the breakage of panels during the construction of new facilities, and damage to panels in existing facilities (weather, breakdowns, design faults, etc.) add to the flow of end-of-life panels to be processed. The volumes of panels reaching their end of life in the years to come will therefore experience exponential growth following the installations that have taken place over the past two decades.

Currently, the panels are collected in Europe via a system financed by the manufacturers and importers of photovoltaic panels. To develop the recycling sector, two main technological paths are available:

- The first way is recycling with low recycled value, only allowing the recovery of the aluminum of the frame of the panels, the cables, and part of the glass. This route makes it possible at best to recover 30% of the value of the materials contained in the panels. It is mainly done by grinding or mechanical crushing. Although 2 industrial units exist in Europe, it has not been demonstrated that this path can be profitable from an economic point of view.
- The second way consists in favoring a more advanced separation of the materials composing the photovoltaic panels in order to access the metals contained inside the photovoltaic cells. The associated methods, including those of ROSI (parent company of which ROSI ALPES is a 100% subsidiary), require a larger initial investment but allow access to the remaining 70% of value contained in the silicon, silver and copper of cells.

None of the few pilot processing lines in place are currently able to fully exploit the value of the materials encapsulated in the modules, mainly pure silicon, and metals such as silver and copper. The main technical challenge is to properly separate these different materials, each of which has high purity and can therefore be recovered.

In the absence of recovery of the materials encapsulated in the photovoltaic modules, all of these materials are lost.

In July 2021, the parent company ROSI (in partnership with Envie 2E Aquitaine) was selected by Soren1 to recycle the silicon, copper and silver contained in end-of-life photovoltaic panels, thanks to its proprietary technologies allowing the recovery of high-value raw materials.

The newly created entity called ROSI ALPES, a 100% subsidiary of ROSI, will be responsible for operating the Saint-Honoré site.

The recycling of these raw materials necessary for the ecological transition (in particular silicon, copper and silver) will make it possible to preserve natural resources.

The figure below illustrates the circular economy and the benefit in terms of natural resources generated by the recovery of end-of-life modules and the recovery of photovoltaic-grade silicon:

FIGURE 2 : ILLUSTRATION OF THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY GENERATED BY THE PROJECT FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF THE MATERIALS CONTAINED IN PHOTOVOLTAIC PANELS

The reintegration of these high value-added raw materials currently lost at the end of their life will greatly reduce the environmental footprint associated with the manufacture of new raw materials (by extraction in mines and use of energy-intensive processes for the transformation of ores) and reduce the associated greenhouse gas emissions.

Thus, the impact of the project on a global scale on the consumption of natural resources will be positive.

2.2.7 Impacts on waste

2.2.7.1 Incoming waste (processed on site)

Incoming waste will be in a solid state. They can be of 2 types:

- Complete photovoltaic panel modules,
- Laminates without aluminum frame, without junction box, and without glass plate.

Waste entering the site is classified as Non-Hazardous waste.

The partnership between the ROSI parent company (of which ROSI ALPES is a 100% subsidiary) and Envie 2E Aquitaine enables photovoltaic treatment to be divided into 2 stages. Envie uses industrial equipment which allows the frame to be removed together with the junction box, then to separate the glass face from the polymer laminate containing the cells.

The glass-free polymer laminate will then be sent to the ROSI ALPES unit, which will proceed with the thermal treatment of the polymers, followed by the chemical separation of the silicon, silver and copper.

ROSI ALPES will be able to receive waste (laminates or photovoltaic panel modules without frames or junction boxes) from the national collection system managed by the eco-organization Soren.

2.2.7.2 Outgoing waste (produced by site activity)

The activity of the ROSI ALPES site will enable the recycling of the following co-products:

- Silicon evacuated in 1,000-liter big bags,
- Silver (recovered in the form of wires) evacuated by fund conveyor,
- Copper (recovered in the form of ribbons) evacuated in dumpsters,
- Glass (in the form of chips or small pieces) evacuated in dumpsters,
- Aluminum (recovered in the form of sections) evacuated in dumpsters,
- possibly aluminum sheets in the case of modules reinforced with aluminum sheets (market share < 1%).

The main **hazardous waste** that will be generated by the activity of recycling used photovoltaic panels will be:

- Liquid effluents from the chemical treatment / etching machine (draining of treatment baths and rinsing baths). Effluents will be evacuated in a 1 m³ container/IBC.
It is likely that this water from the treatment and rinsing baths could be recycled in the wet scrubber of the atmospheric effluents of the pyrolysis furnace. Thus, depending on the results of the tests that will be carried out after the commissioning of the planned installations, these effluents may perhaps be recycled on the site and may not have to be evacuated.
- Waste in the form of sludge, which will be evacuated in watertight pallet boxes 600L
- Sieved dust and fines (powdery materials from the process that cannot be treated, and therefore lost in the form of dust),
- Dust collected in the big bags present on the 2 dust collectors.

Non-hazardous waste may be generated in very small quantities by the staff occupying the offices (paper, cardboard, household waste, etc.). This waste will be sorted by staff.

The packaging (cardboard, plastic) and plastic straps used to wrap the panels on the pallets received will be placed in the containers of Evolutionary Space.

Empty pallets will be returned to their sender for reuse.

2.2.8 Traffic impacts

The industrial zone of the Marais on which the company ROSI ALPES will be established is accessible from the national road RN85, by the D115C from the south or by the D114D from the North (Grenoble).

The average annual daily traffic on the D115C was 700 vehicles per day in 2018. The average annual daily traffic on the RN 85 was 6,000 vehicles per day.

Please note that vehicles with a gross vehicle weight (GVW) greater than 7.5 tons are prohibited on the Descente de Laffrey. Only vehicles whose height is less than 2.60 m can pass freely through the control gate. Trucks with a GVW of more than 7.5 t leaving the site in the direction of Grenoble will therefore have to take the load shedding route via the RD529, taking the RN85 towards the south. RD529 currently supports traffic of 3,400 vehicles per day, including 5.3% heavy goods vehicles.

The traffic generated by the activity of the ROSI ALPES site will mainly be linked to:

- Deliveries by heavy goods vehicles of incoming waste (laminates and modules of photovoltaic panels without frames or junction boxes) and chemicals,
- HGV removals of co-products (silicon, silver, copper and glass) and waste,
- Light vehicles (LV) for staff (20 employees) and visitors, i.e. approximately 30 light vehicles per day.

Depending on the type of end-of-life photovoltaic panels that will be received (laminates or modules) and the possibility of recycling the effluents from the rinsing machine in the wet scrubber, the number **of truck rotations will be between 241 and 371 per year (i.e. 1 to 2 truck rotations per day on average).**

As far as light vehicles are concerned, **30 light vehicle rotations per day are considered.**

The increase in traffic will mainly be felt on the roads serving the Espace Evolutif (the D115C or the D114D). Traffic will mainly consist of light staff and visitor vehicles. The number of trucks will be limited (1 to 2 per day on average).

Once the vehicles have reached larger axes (RN85 or RD529), the impact of the project will be very low (increase of less than 2% and traffic consisting mainly of light vehicles).

2.2.9 Effects on sound levels

The sound environment before the commissioning of the ROSI ALPES site is mainly impacted by boiler making work from the workshops located in the western part of the Espace Evolutif building.

Added to this is the road traffic noise generated by the various vehicles passing over the site, as well as on the roads located nearby.

As part of this file, a 3D acoustic modeling study was carried out by a specialized company in order to determine the provisions to be made so that the sound levels generated by the activity of the planned site comply with the regulations in force.

These provisions are as follows:

- The installation of processing equipment inside a building,
- The presence of partitioning of the various workshops (with sound-absorbing partitions which reduce sound levels),
- The closing of doors and windows,
- The choice of low-noise equipment or the installation of acoustic improvement devices (silencers on the chimneys and on the grille of the compressor room, cowling of the 2 air extractors located outside the rooms).

The site will comply with the regulations in force and in particular the decree of 23/01/1997 relating to the limitation of noise emitted into the environment by installations classified for the protection of the environment which defines sound levels not to be exceeded in property line and at the level of the nearest dwellings (called Regulated Emergence Zones).

A sound level measurement campaign will be carried out within 6 months of the start of the activity to check compliance with this decree. Then a measurement will be carried out every 2 years.

2.2.10 Impacts resulting from vibrations

The activities and equipment of ROSI ALPES will not lead to vibrations that can be felt by the neighborhood.

2.2.11 Air impacts

Photovoltaic panel processing activities will be the source of the following emissions:

- Effluents from the pyrolysis and post-combustion chambers (1),
- Effluents from the residue cooling chamber at the outlet of the pyrolysis furnace (4),
- Effluents from the mechanical separation workshop (2),
- Effluents from the chemical treatment/etching workshop (3).

2.2.11.1 Effluents from the pyrolysis and post-combustion chambers,

The heat treatment of laminates and modules of photovoltaic panels without frames and without junction boxes is carried out in a pyrolysis furnace to which is associated a post-combustion chamber.

The plastic materials present will be “pyrolyzed” (which corresponds to thermal degradation) in the pyrolysis chamber and transformed into “combustible gases” which will then be burned at 850°C in the post-combustion chamber.

The optimization of the design of the furnace (in terms of temperature and turbulence of the fumes, post-combustion air flows, etc.) and the use of an automatic computerized system for controlling the efficiency of the combustion make it possible to improve the environmental performance of the furnace and limit the formation of atmospheric pollutants. These techniques are part of the Best Available Techniques to reduce the formation of atmospheric pollutants at the source.

The after burning of the pyrolysis gases generates gaseous effluents (carbon oxides, nitrogen oxides, hydrogen fluoride due to the presence of fluorine in the polymers, water vapor, etc.) and particulates (which may contain metals from incoming waste or carbonaceous dust).

Before being discharged through a 13 m high chimney (chimney no. 1), the effluents from the afterburner chamber will be washed by a system combining a quench (for cooling the fumes) and a 2-stage scrubber using a soda solution to trap the pollutants contained in the fumes by absorption.

The pollutant concentrations in the effluents will comply with the limit values defined in French regulations.

For certain pollutants, ROSI ALPES even requests limit values (concentrations not to be exceeded in ROSI ALPES discharges) lower than those defined by the regulations:

- That required for the sum of the metals is, depending on the metals, 2 to 10 times lower than the regulatory value,
- Those requested for hydrogen chloride, ammonia, sulfur dioxide and dioxins/furans are 10 times lower than the regulatory value,
- That requested for mercury is 100 times lower than the regulatory value.

Indeed, according to the bibliography and the studies available, the solar modules do not contain any of these substances or atoms of chlorine, nitrogen, sulfur, etc. likely to generate emissions of such substances. This is the reason why concentrations below the regulatory limits were considered.

It should be noted that the tests carried out on 01/27/2022 on the ROSI pilot line show that the PCDD/ PCDF concentrations expected at the outlet of the pyrolysis furnace will be approximately twice as low as the Emission Limit Values requested, themselves even 10 times lower than those defined in the regulations.

Discharges through the wet scrubber stack will be subject to continuous monitoring by ROSI ALPES. In addition, ROSI ALPES will have 4 discharge analyzes carried out by an independent accredited organization during the first year of operation, then 2 analyses per year beyond the first year.

A program to monitor the impact of these discharges on the environment in the vicinity of the site will be set up by ROSI ALPES. The program will notably provide for the determination of the concentration of pollutants in the environment:

- before commissioning the installation (zero point),
- within a period of between 3 and 6 months after commissioning of the installation.
- after the initial period, at least once a year.

2.2.11.2 Effluents from the cooling zone at the outlet of the pyrolysis furnace and the mechanical separation

In order to avoid uncontrolled dust emissions, the cooling and handling of powdery residues will be carried out in a dedicated area inside the building.

In addition, dust removal systems will be implemented to capture the dust carried away during these processes.

Filtration equipment will be selected according to the nature and type of particles likely to be emitted.

Dust removal will be carried out by 2 systems using filter cartridges positioned in the workshop and each connected to a chimney 10 m high. The dust will be collected in big bags and evacuated as waste.

The pollutant concentrations in the effluents will comply with the limit values defined in French regulations with regard to dust emissions.

ROSI ALPES even requests limit values 20 times lower than the regulatory values and will comply with the Best Available Techniques (BAT) for channeled atmospheric dust emissions for the incineration of waste (BAT defined at European level), although these very restrictive levels are not applicable to the project.

ROSI ALPES also requests Emission Limit Values (ELV) for the substances Pb, Sn, Si, Al, Ag, TiO₂ and for their sum. The requested ELVs correspond to the values used in the Health Risk Assessment.

ROSI ALPES will have an analysis of the discharges carried out by an accredited and independent organization in the year following the commissioning of the installation. Then a measurement will then be carried out every 6 months.

2.2.11.3 Effluents from the chemical treatment / etching workshop

The baskets containing the fragments of filtered solar cells resulting from the mechanical separation will be sent to the engraving machine which contains in particular treatment baths. The gaseous effluent is sucked by a fan towards a chimney.

The gaseous effluents from the workshop will only contain vapors related to the use of chemicals in the baths, which have no environmental or health impact.

It will be released by a chimney 10 m high.

2.2.11.4 Vehicle exhaust emissions

Diffuse emissions of exhaust gases by vehicles will be very limited and without impact on air quality since the traffic generated by the site will be very low: 30 light vehicles per day and 1 to 2 heavy goods vehicles per day on average.

2.2.12 Energy consumption

2.2.12.1 Origin of energy consumption

The site's main energy sources will be:

- **electricity** : The site is supplied with 400 volts by the public electricity network. No electrical transformer is present on the ROSI ALPES site.
- **propane** used as fuel in the pyrolysis and post-combustion chambers and for space heating. It will be stored in underground tanks (which will not be operated by ROSI ALPES) and will supply the manufacturing building with buried pipes.

2.2.12.2 Energetic efficiency

Consumption of electricity

The main electricity consuming items will be:

- incoming waste processing equipment (motors, pumps, conveyors, fans, compressor...),
- atmospheric effluent treatment devices (wet scrubber and dust collectors, and associated extractors),
- the reversible heat pump (offices, meeting room, changing rooms, refectory, etc.), the VMCs in the tertiary premises, as well as the system for destratification of the hot air accumulated on the roof which will be used in winter.

The main measures taken to limit electricity consumption are:

- The use of equipment powered by high-efficiency electric motors of suitable power (in order to limit their operation at idle or at low load),
- Lighting of premises and outdoor areas using LED devices (which consume less electricity than incandescent bulbs, halogens or even compact fluorescent lamps).
- The operation of the exterior lighting will be controlled by an astrological clock allowing the lighting to be triggered according to the times of sunrise and sunset (variable from day to day). This system will be supplemented by natural light detection (luxmeter).
- The operation of the gate lighting will be slaved to the opening of the latter.

Propane consumption

75% of propane consumption will be used as fuel in the pyrolysis furnace, the rest (25%) for space heating by unit heaters.

Part of the energy produced by the combustion of propane and pyrolysis gases will be lost:

- By the radiation of the pyrolysis furnace when it is at high temperature,
- By the calories contained in the hot smoke evacuated by the chimney.

Pyrolysis Furnace Radiation Losses

The measures planned to limit these losses are as follows:

- Optimization of the insulation of the oven (requested from the supplier),
- Optimization by ROSI ALPES of the maximum operating temperature during the pyrolysis cycle, in order to limit the power and duration of these losses.

The optimization of the design of the furnace chamber (in terms of temperature and turbulence of the fumes, post-combustion air flows, etc.) and the use of an automatic computerized system for controlling the efficiency of combustion will also improve the overall environmental performance of waste incineration, and limit propane consumption

Initially, ROSI ALPES did not plan to recover these thermal losses for technical and economic reasons. Indeed, ROSI ALPES's main challenge for this industry first is to demonstrate the economic viability of the high value-added recycling process for end-of-life photovoltaic panel waste. With this in mind, ROSI ALPES relies on existing industrial equipment intended for other uses.

The heat radiated by the furnace will be used to heat the factory premises in winter via fans to prevent the accumulation of hot air in the upper part, and thus to diffuse the heat throughout the workshop. On the other hand, during the summer period, the hot air accumulated in the upper part of the building above the furnace will be evacuated by an extraction turret installed on the roof.

Losses in hot fumes

Initially, no system for recovering the energy contained in the flue gases is planned.

Indeed, before their treatment by the wet scrubber, the atmospheric effluents from the pyrolysis furnace contain acid gases, too aggressive for a possible heat recovery exchanger.

ROSI ALPES plans to take temperature readings in order to size a possible heat recovery. A heat recovery device could be installed if the environmental benefit and the economic viability are demonstrated from the data collected during the first years of operation of the recycling site.

2.2.13 Impacts of the project on the climate and of the vulnerability of the project to climate change

2.2.13.1 Climate change

Causes and effects of climate change

Greenhouse gases (GHGs) play an essential role in regulating the climate. Without them, the average temperature on Earth would be -18°C instead of +14°C and life might not exist. However, since the 19th century, man has considerably increased the quantity of greenhouse gases present in the atmosphere. Consequently, the natural climatic balance is modified, and the climate is readjusted by a warming of the earth's surface.

The main foreseeable effects of climate change are:

- the increase in the average global temperature,
- the rise in sea level and ocean temperature,
- the aggravation of climatic phenomena: the evolution of the climate modifies the frequency, intensity, geographical distribution and duration of extreme meteorological events (storms, floods, droughts),
- Disruption of many ecosystems: with the extinction of animal and plant species, and significant consequences for human settlements.

2.2.13.2 Impacts of the project on the climate

Project-related greenhouse gas emissions will mainly consist of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions contained in the atmospheric effluents from the pyrolysis furnace. These emissions will be linked to:

- Combustion of propane used as fuel in the pyrolysis furnace,
- The thermal degradation of the polymers presents in the pyrolyzed waste.

Carbon dioxide emissions related to vehicle traffic generated by the site will be low (the average daily traffic will be only 30 light vehicles and 1 to 2 heavy goods vehicles).

It should be noted that the photovoltaic panel recycling project is part of a broader **circular economy** objective allowing the regeneration of:

- Silicon,
- Copper,
- Aluminum,
- Silver.

None of the few pilot processing lines for end-of-life photovoltaic panels that have been put in place are currently able to fully exploit the value of the materials encapsulated in the modules, mainly pure silicon, and metals such as silver and copper. **In the absence of recovery of the materials encapsulated in the photovoltaic modules, all of these materials are lost.**

In contrast, the revaluation by ROSI ALPES of silicon, silver, copper and glass will make it possible to reduce greenhouse gas emissions associated with the manufacture of new raw materials (by extraction in mines and the use of energy-intensive processes for the transformation of ores).

By way of illustration, the recovery of silicon by ROSI ALPES (at a purity of 99.999%) will emit 40 to 50 times less CO₂ than the production in China of silicon 1,000 times less pure (purity of 99%).

Thus, even if ROSI ALPES's activity will generate greenhouse gas emissions, the overall impact of the project on the climate will be positive.

2.2.13.3 Impact of project vulnerability to climate change

The project is not vulnerable to increases in air or ocean temperature, or sea level rise.

The only vulnerability of the project to climate change is its exposure to extreme climatic phenomena (storms, floods, drought) which could be aggravated.

However, the buildings comply with the rules that were in force when they were built and are protected against the effects of storms (wind, snow, lightning, etc.). The site is in a low hazard zone with regard to the phenomenon of shrinkage-swelling of clay (which can damage buildings), and far from forest fire zones.

The southern part of ROSI ALPES is located in a sector affected by a risk of plain flooding. In the event of flooding, the operation of the workshops concerned would be temporarily suspended and the products or waste presenting a risk of pollution for the environment would be transferred to the zone further north of the ROSI ALPES building which is not located in the flood zone.

The fence that will be installed to separate ROSI ALPES from the southern sector of Espace Evolutif will not create any obstacle to the circulation of water in the event of flooding.

The site and its activities are not very vulnerable to climate change. The risk of impact on the project due to climate change is negligible.

2.2.14 Impacts on landscapes

The buildings of the Espace Evolutif, within which the project will be located, are visible in the near field from the roads along the site: Route de la Mouche (D114D) to the south, Route du

Tabor (D115C) to the east and Prés des Sagnes to the north. They are then masked by vegetation and constructions as the point of view recedes.

It should be noted that the facades (currently of disparate aspects) will be standardized by the Community of Communes of Matheysine within the framework of the operations of partial demolition, rehabilitation and change of destination of the modular rental workshops which have been the subject a building permit issued on 09/22/2017 by the municipality of Saint-Honoré.

White will be the only color of the facades. The concrete foundations of the platforms will be painted brown dark.

The demolition operations have already been carried out in 2018 by the Community of Communes. These works are independent of the project, and the company ROSI ALPES will take place in the premises after this renovation.

The main changes visible from the outside, which ROSI ALPES will make, will relate to:

- The addition of 4 stacks for atmospheric effluent discharges, the heights of which will be included between 10 and 13 m (for buildings culminating at 8.5 m),
- The addition of an extractor whose exhaust will be located at a height of 10 m and intended to purification of the ambient air in the chemical storage room,
- The addition of a safety device allowing the venting of pyrolysis gases, which the exhaust will be located at a height of 10 meters,
- The addition of a fence and an access gate in the yard. This fence will be inside Evolutionary Space, it is not a perimeter fence to Evolutionary Space. However, this one will be of the same type in white welded mesh, in order to avoid having fences of disparate aspects.
- The addition of a limited amount of equipment on the facade, particularly associated with the treatment of gas from pyrolysis.

The perception of the site will therefore only be slightly modified. The visual impact of the project will be very low.

2.2.15 Impacts resulting from light emissions

As part of the rehabilitation and change of destination operations of the modular rental workshops of the Evolutive Space, the Community of Communes of Matheysine modifies the exterior lighting at the same time as the facades.

The lighting in the courtyard of sector 4 where the ROSI ALPES company will be located will be modified according to the same principles as the rest of the building. 6 LED projectors will be set up (mainly located near the access doors), including 1 on the access gate which will be set up.

The lighting will be chosen in line with the needs in terms of required intensity and moving towards types of products that do not present any dazzling character for the neighborhood and also limit diffusion towards the sky. The lights will be directed downwards.

The operation of the exterior lighting will be controlled by an astrological clock which allows the lighting to be triggered according to the times of sunrise and sunset (variable from day to day). This system will be supplemented by natural light detection (luxmeter).

The operation of the gate lighting will be slaved to its opening.

Given the planned provisions, the impact of the site resulting from light emissions will remain low.

2.2.16 Impacts on cultural heritage

No sensitive heritage issue has been identified within a radius of 2 km around the project site.

The project's impact on cultural heritage is therefore nil.

2.2.17 Impact of the project on health

As part of the project to create a photovoltaic panel recycling site, a health risk assessment process was conducted in order to assess the possible impact of planned activities on the health of populations neighboring the project.

Although not required by regulation, a **quantitative** impact assessment was conducted (not just a qualitative assessment).

The emission sources used are the atmospheric emissions from the 3 stacks through which the atmospheric effluents from:

- The pyrolysis furnace effluent scrubber,
- The cooling zone effluent dust collector,
- The effluent dust extractor from the mechanical separation workshop.
-

Atmospheric emissions from chemical etching treatment are insignificant.

The exposure scenarios studied are as follows:

- Inhalation of gases and particles emitted into the atmosphere,
- Ingestion of soil exposed to the fallout of particles from atmospheric emissions,
- Ingestion of plants exposed to the fallout of particles from atmospheric emissions.

The substances emitted by chimneys and included in this study are as follows:

- Dust,
- Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂),

- Sulfur dioxide (SO₂),
- Hydrogen fluoride (HF),
- Metals (Arsenic, silver, chromium, cobalt, copper, nickel and lead),
- Dioxins and furans,
- Titanium dioxide (TiO₂),
- Volatile organic compounds (acetaldehyde and benzene).

Modeling of the atmospheric dispersion of the releases was carried out. It takes into account local meteorological data and relief. The results of the modeling (concentrations in the air and deposition of particles on the ground) were then interpreted in terms of impact on air quality and health impact on populations.

Chronic exposure scenarios by inhalation and ingestion (of soils and/or plants) were constructed from the results of the modeling at the level of neighboring homes/businesses.

The calculations show that the risk indicators calculated on the basis of globally upper assumptions comply with the benchmark acceptability values for the threshold effects (expressing the possibility of occurrence of toxic effects associated with the substance due to exposure considered) **and for non- threshold effects** (corresponding to the additional probability that the human organism has of developing the effect associated with the substance due to the exposure considered).

Indeed, at the level of the most exposed receptor, taking into account exposure by inhalation and by ingestion of all tracer pollutants:

- the Hazard Quotients (HQ) calculated for the threshold effects are equal to 0.060 and 0.042 for the child and adult targets respectively, which is much lower than the reference value of 1 (by one factor of approximately 16 to 24).
- the excess individual risk (ERI) calculated for the non-threshold effects are equal to 1.6×10^{-8} and 6.5×10^{-8} for, respectively, child and adult targets, which are much lower than the benchmark value of 10^{-5} (by a factor of approximately 150 to 625).

Modeled dust, nitrogen dioxide and sulfur dioxide concentrations are also below WHO Recommended Air Quality Levels (latest 2021 recommendations).

Thus, according to the calculations carried out and taking into account the current state of knowledge and the accepted reference criteria, the risks attributable to the discharges from the project of the ROSI ALPES company can be considered "not of concern" according to the French methodology for the assessment of risks.

An analysis of the uncertainties was carried out on the main stages of this study, highlighting the absence of hypotheses or uncertainties likely to call into question the conclusions of the study.

2.2.18 Analysis of cumulative effects with other existing or approved projects

An analysis of the cumulative effects of the ROSI ALPES project with other existing or approved projects was carried out.

One project has been identified near the ROSI ALPES project:

- A ground-mounted photovoltaic power plant project led by the company GEG Energie in the town of Susville,

The cumulative effects of the ROSI ALPES project with this project is analyzed in the following paragraph.

2.2.18.1 Ground-mounted photovoltaic power plant project

The location of this ground-mounted photovoltaic power plant project is not precisely known within the municipality of Susville, but it is located approximately 900 m from the ROSI ALPES project.

Given this minimum distance of 900 m and the nature of this project, **no cumulative effect is expected with the ROSI ALPES photovoltaic panel recycling site project.**

2.3 Impact resulting from vulnerability of the project to risks accidents of major disasters.

The accidental risks are analyzed with regard to the information available from the following documents:

- Major Risks Departmental File (DDRM) of Isère dating from 2020,
- Description of the risks of the Georisques2 site (edited on 03/08/2021).

The project therefore does not present any particular vulnerability to the risk of major accidents or disasters, with the exception of the risk of flooding in the southern part of the site.

In the event of flooding, the operation of the workshops located in the flood zone would be temporarily suspended. Products or waste presenting a risk of pollution for the environment would be transferred to the area further north of the ROSI ALPES building, which is located outside the flood zone.

In the southern part of the site, the fence that will be installed to separate ROSI ALPES from the southern sector of Espace Evolutif will not create any obstacle to the circulation of water in the event of flooding.

There will therefore be no associated impacts.

2.4 Description of reasonable alternatives examined and the main reason for the choice made

The impact study must justify the choices made with regard to the foreseeable effects of the project on the environment.

The main alternative studied by the parent company ROSI for its ROSI ALPES project concerns the choice of location of the site.

ROSI has a complete prototype line for its R&D activities relating to the recycling of photovoltaic panels on its experimental platform in Grenoble. This industrial platform has been made available by Grenoble-Alpes University for technology startups since December 2020. This is why ROSI initially sought to establish itself in the Grenoble conurbation.

Given the difficulty of finding rental premises, with a surface area and configuration adapted to the project (at a reasonable cost), ROSI has widened its scope of research.

Following the requalification of its site, Espace Evolutif has modular premises (from 90 m² to more than 1,000 m²) whose configuration is adapted to the project. It also has the advantage of being far from crèches, schools, retirement homes and health establishments.

There is no hospital, retirement home or kindergarten within a radius of 2 km. The nearest primary school is 1.5 km away.

The number of nearby dwellings is limited to a few dwellings.

Thus, the selected site complies with article 3 of the decree of September 20, 2002 relating to installations for the incineration and co-incineration of non-hazardous waste and installations incinerating waste from health care activities with infectious risks which indicates that : “The choice of the location takes into account the analysis of the foreseeable, direct and indirect, temporary and permanent effects of the installation on the environment and on health, in particular with regard to the immediate proximity of dwellings. , nurseries, schools, retirement homes and health establishments and the general conditions for the dispersion of discharges”.

2.5 Condition for restoration of the site after operation

In accordance with the regulations, the impact study presents the principles that would be implemented in the event of cessation of activity of the planned facilities.

In accordance with article R. 512-39-1 of the Environmental Code, in the event of permanent shutdown, the operator would notify the Prefect of the date of this shutdown 3 months before it. This notification would present the operations planned in this context.

During the final shutdown of the site, the site will be made safe.

All of the photovoltaic panels that have begun to undergo pyrolysis would be treated to the end of the process (mechanical separation then chemical treatment) in order to financially enhance the materials (particularly silicon, copper and silver).

The chemical treatment baths and the wet scrubber of atmospheric effluents from the pyrolysis furnace would be drained. Unopened IBCs of chemicals would be returned to suppliers.

The waste generated by the facilities (liquid effluents, sludge, dust and sieved fines) would be treated by appropriate channels.

Equipment can be sold. The premises would be returned to their owner, the Community of Communes of Matheysine. All fluids (water, electricity, propane) will be stopped.

The preventive measures listed in the file represent security with regard to the protection of the ground and the subsoil. These include in particular the storage of liquid products on retentions.

The studies (pollution diagnosis) necessary for the restoration of the site, as well as any soil and groundwater depollution work that may prove necessary, would be carried out by ROSI ALPES.

